

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYZING THE PROBLEMS OF STABILITY OF THE NATIONAL CURRENCY EXCHANGE RATE OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

At this stage, the consequences of the global geopolitical crisis continue to negatively affect the global economy, which is characterized by a high degree of instability and inconsistency in the economic policies of the largest countries and integration structures. The current situation threatens problems in the global economy and makes its future extremely uncertain. One of the main reasons for such uncertainty is the instability of the global monetary system (MFS) caused by the uncontrolled expansion of financial markets and financial instruments, the liberalization of international capital flows, the growing influence of transnational financial institutions on developing economies and the dollarization of the global economy. As a result, the structural principles of the Jamaican monetary system, developed in the 1960s in the interests of the United States and other developed countries, no longer correspond to the realities of the global economy. In this regard, the issue of reforming the Ministry of Internal Affairs and regulating international monetary relations is becoming important. Modern scientific research examines various approaches to the reform of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. These include reducing the role of the dollar as the dominant international currency, the formation of a polycentric world order and the creation of a monetary union to diversify international currency liquidity. This is due to the fact that the monetary policy of each country is not independent, but is an integral part of the monetary system and economic policy as a whole. Therefore, currency integration requires a well-established common economic policy of all participating countries, including Kazakhstan. The stability of the country's national currency is becoming an important factor in the development of the national economy and ensuring economic growth, since its fluctuations have a certain impact not only on financial markets, but also on other sectors of the economy. And in the current situation of instability, the study of this issue will reveal the problems and effective direction of state policy aimed at ensuring the economic security of the country and the possibility of stabilizing the exchange rate.

Keywords: national currency, economic security, inflation, balance of payments, discount rate, currency policy.

Introduction

Currency stability is one of the final and most important indicators of the effectiveness of foreign economic activity and international competitiveness of the country's economy. The Republic of Kazakhstan (RK) has become a full-fledged subject of the world economic system, including closer integration relations within the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU). Since the introduction of the national currency - tenge, its constant depreciation has been recorded. In this regard, the study of the stability of the exchange rate of the country, the development of the monetary system of the country, the prospects of integration into the global and regional economy, as well as the effectiveness of monetary policy, on which depends the success of sustainable economic growth.

Studies on the study of the monetary and financial system of the RK and the processes of currency integration within the EAEU were conducted in the works of economists: N.A. Nazarbayev, N.T. Sailaubekov, A.F. Khapilin, V.Y. Dodonov, R.E. Elemesov, L.N. Krasavina, N.A. Nurseit, V.G. Kabetenova, E.K. Smanov, A.V. Khamzaeva and others. Nazarbek U.B., Tulegenova M.O., Kalbaeva N.T. Bimendiev L., Bazhikova G., Ibragimova, N. V. [1,2,3] in their studies

paid much attention to the factors influencing the exchange rate of the national currency. Dodonov V.Y. considered the hypothesis of dependence of the rate of the national currency of Kazakhstan on the Russian currency in connection with the countries' membership in the EAEU [4].

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to identify the problems of stability of the national currency exchange rate and identify promising areas for improving the effectiveness of monetary regulation, taking into account international experience in the conditions of instability and transformation of the modern international monetary system, intensification of currency integration processes in the world, as well as within the framework of the Eurasian Economic Union.

Materials and methods of research

The conceptual basis of the study is presented in the modern works of foreign and Kazakh economists, devoted to the MBS and monetary and financial regulation. The validity of the results is based on general scientific methods, such as analytical and systematic approaches, comparative analysis, structural analysis, statistical analysis, correlation analysis, historical and

logical analysis, inductive and deductive, systematization and graphical analysis.

The information and empirical base of the study is represented by the works of domestic and foreign scientists, statistical data and analytical reviews of international and national organizations: International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank, the World Gold Council, the European Central Bank, the Bank of England, Japan, the US Federal Reserve System, the National Bank of Kazakhstan, the Central Banks of the member countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (EAEU).

The results of the study and their discussion

Currency in Italian means money (*valuta*). National currency is a currency issued by the state or central bank in the territory of this state, which is used for

settlements and payments, foreign economic relations and international settlements with other countries. Since the introduction of the tenge as the national currency of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there has been a tendency to its constant depreciation. Thus, in 1993 one dollar cost 4.7 tenge, which was the highest rate of tenge. By 1999, the dollar had already increased from 84 to 138 tenge. For 2018 the average rate of tenge to dollar was 344.7 tenge, for August 2019 the dollar cost 386.67 tenge, for 2023 was 476.98 tenge, that is, the Kazakh national currency has depreciated more than 80 times. The rates of the U.S. dollar, euro and Japanese yen fluctuate slightly. Let's consider internal and external criteria of stability of the national currency (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Criteria of national currency stability

World oil prices are one of the main factors affecting the exchange rate of the tenge. In 2018, oil accounted for 62% of Kazakhstan's exports. Changes in the crude oil exchange rate are closely linked to the global economic cycle. For example, as a result of the Asian financial crisis of 1997-1998 and the fall in world oil and metal prices, the tenge began to fall rapidly from 1999. In the period from 2003 to 2007, the tenge gradually strengthened as world commodity markets saw a steady rise in prices. Against the backdrop of the global economic crisis in 2008, when there were massive bank failures and falling stock prices in the U.S., the dollar exchange rate in Kazakhstan rose from KZT120 to KZT150. In early 2014, the fall in oil prices by almost 60% contributed to a sharp devaluation of the tenge in 2015 to 185 tenge, in 2016 the dollar cost 340 tenge. With the advent of the pandemic in 2020, the country experienced a fourth devaluation, with the dollar rising

to 400 tenge. Economic crisis in 2022 due to the Russian-Ukrainian military conflict there was a fifth devaluation. Undoubtedly, the US dollar is the main currency for settlements in the oil and gas industry, which leads to its most frequent use for domestic transactions, and this leads to increased dependence of the national currency.

The consequences of unfavorable changes in commodity markets are reflected in the country's economic growth (Figure 2).

According to the indicators in Figure 2, a direct correlation between the dynamics of oil prices and GDP of the RK is confirmed. As a result of the global financial crisis in 2008 and the subsequent sharp drop in oil prices, the real GDP growth rate of Kazakhstan in 2009 decreased to 1.2%, in 2016 to 1.1%, and in 2020 to -2.6% [5].

Figure 2: Dynamics of oil prices and GDP in Kazakhstan 1998-2022.

According to analysts of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), global geopolitical tensions (relations between the United States and China and the situation in Ukraine) may lead to a reduction in cross-border investment and banking operations, which in turn will have a negative impact on the economy as a whole and reduce its growth by 2% [6].

The Governing Council of the European Central Bank raised the key rate to 3.5% in March 2022. The bank attributed this increase to rising inflation. It is expected to remain high for quite a long time, while the main goal of both the Fed and the ECB is ultimately the intention to reduce inflation to 2%. ECB analysts predict that the inflation rate could "come down" to 2.1% by 2025. The decision to raise interest rates was made by the Central Bank of England - the bank's rate rose to 4.25%. The rate of the Central Bank of New Zealand was 5.25%, the Reserve Bank of Australia - 3.6%, the Central Bank of Pakistan - 21%. When interest rates rise, saving becomes more profitable than consumption, business and personal spending declines, credit becomes expensive, and this slows economic growth. As a result, a slowing economy leads to lower inflation. According to an analysis by International Monetary

Fund (IMF) economists John Mark Natal and Philip Barrett, rising interest rates are temporary. "Once inflation is back under control, advanced economy central banks are likely to loosen monetary policy and return real interest rates to pre-pandemic levels," the IMF analysts said. According to statistics, since the fourth quarter of 2022, the National Bank of Kazakhstan holds the highest prime rate in the EAEU - 16%. This means that loans in Kazakhstan are the most expensive, and this affects all areas of the economy [7].

One of the internal criteria is the balance of payments, which is a report reflecting all foreign economic transactions of the country with other countries of the world for the reporting period. Thus, according to the data of the NB RK the balance of payments at the end of the first quarter of 2023 was formed with a deficit of \$1.6 billion. At the end of the first quarter of 2022 there was a surplus of \$4.8 billion. The decrease in exports is due to the decline in exports of oil and gas condensate by 25.7% or \$3.5 billion.

Inflation in the Republic of Kazakhstan in September 2023 for the year slowed down and amounted to 11.8% (Table 1) [5].

Table 1

Inflation in the Republic of Kazakhstan (%)			
	2021	2022	2023
Annual inflation	8,9	17,7	11,8
Food products	11,5	22,2	11,4
Non-food products	6,8	17,0	11,9
Paid services	7,5	12,3	11,9

The greatest contribution to inflation is made by foodstuffs, as their share in the consumer basket is about 40%, and it includes goods that are strongly influenced by seasonality. In addition, non-food products also make a significant contribution to domestic price inflation due to high dependence on imports and instability of exchange rates. The contribution of services to inflation is the smallest, mainly reflecting price control by state monopolies through tariffs. The reason for high

inflation in Kazakhstan compared to neighboring countries is due to:

1. Commodity dependence. First of all, it concerns the price of oil on global markets. A significant drop in energy prices leads to a sharp deterioration in the balance of payments, causing a weakening of the national currency and rising inflation.

2. Inadequate fiscal policy and lack of financial discipline. Explanation. In favorable periods of high oil prices, the government should reduce financing of

budget expenditures by setting aside money in the National Fund (Natsfond). On the other hand, when oil prices fall, budget revenues fall, budget deficit deepens and, as a consequence, the national currency weakens. In turn, the weakening of national currencies leads to an increase in prices for imported goods. In case of a sharp and prolonged decline in the price of oil, the government must use money from the National Fund to maintain public expenditures at the same level. Also, the government, selling foreign currency from the National Fund at the local currency exchange does not allow the national currency to depreciate, which in turn reduces the growth of inflation in the country.

Absence of competition. Competition stimulates the efficient use and distribution of resources in the economy, thereby causing price reductions and lower inflation. In addition, key commodity markets are dominated by large state-owned enterprises (JSC NC KazMunayGas, Air Astana, JSC Kazakhtelecom, JSC Otbasy Bank, JSC NC Kazakhstan Temir Zholy) and several private companies associated with the state. Very often the government does not provide equal conditions between public and private companies.

Insufficiently developed financial and currency market in Kazakhstan. One of the key factors hindering the development of the financial market in Kazakhstan is government financing at an interest rate much lower than the market rate. This practice reduces the efficiency of money distribution in the economy, creates unfair competition in the financial market and sharply reduces the effectiveness of interest rate and credit channels of inflation management by the National Bank.

Kazakhstan ranks 15th in the world in terms of confirmed commercial gold reserves and third in the CIS, after Russia and Uzbekistan. Gold reserves in Kazakhstan fell to 314 tons in the second quarter of 2023. The maximum reserves reached 402 tons in 2022, and the minimum 221 tons in 2015. These reserves for the period of crisis ensure the stability of the national economy and allow the state to solve many problems without external borrowing [8].

In the field of foreign exchange policy, the National Bank will retain the regime of free-floating exchange rate. To increase transparency and confidence in the policy, the National Bank regularly publishes the volume of allocated transfers and converted assets from the National Fund in the foreign exchange market.

Building up the attractiveness of tenge deposits by means of interest rates contributed to the further process of dedollarization in the banking system and facilitated the increase in funding of second-tier banks in the national currency. However, dollarization remains a challenge as the leading intervention currency is the dollar. As of January 1, 2023, the banking sector of the Republic of Kazakhstan is represented by 21 second-tier banks, including 12 banks with foreign participation, including 8 subsidiary banks. The top five large banks are Halyk Bank of Kazakhstan, KASPI BANK, Bank CenterCredit, Otbasy Bank and ForteBank. According to the Kazakhstan Agency for Regulation and Development of Financial Market (ARDF), in March 2023 deposits in tenge of commercial banks increased

by 3.7% to 21.6 trillion KZT, in foreign currency - only by 1.3% to 9.1 trillion KZT. As a result, the level of dollarization decreased and by April 1 was 29.8% compared to 31.6% at the beginning of 2023. According to R. Dosov, chief analyst of the Association of Financiers of Kazakhstan, the reason for the decrease in dollarization of deposits is due to low non-market rates on dollar deposits at the level of 1% and high yield of tenge deposits at 18.3%, which in addition were charged an additional 10% from the state under the Tenge Deposit Protection Program [10]

Conclusions

Thus, the stability of the tenge has a great impact on the economic security of Kazakhstan. Since the introduction of tenge into circulation, its exchange rate has been decreasing. This is based on internal rather than external factors. The main problem of Kazakhstan's economy is the low level of diversification. As a result, it is dependent on the oil sector, and the inflow of foreign currency is provided mainly by the oil sector. Significant fluctuations in world oil prices have a significant impact on Kazakhstan's trade, balance of payments, budget and economic growth. It is necessary to diversify export flows away from narrowly oriented exports and reduce imports of goods by increasing domestic production potential. Tighten control over the spending of budget funds and implementation of investment projects carried out under the state program. Strengthen the fight against excessive bureaucracy and corruption in state bodies that control and supervise import-export and commercial activities [6].

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